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Research Article

**DIAGNOSIS AND MANAGEMENT OF ACUTE ISCHEMIC
STROKE IN PAKISTAN.**¹Dr Ujala Khalid,²Dr Adeel Ahmad, ³Dr Qurat-ul-ain.¹MBBS, Fatima Jinnah Medical University, Lahore.²MBBS, Shalamar Medical and Dental College, Lahore.³MBBS, Quaid e Azam Medical College, Bahawalpur.**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

Stroke is the second largest leading cause of death worldwide. Though the stroke incidence is high in the West but probably it is rising in Asia. The burden of stroke is immense and a report stated that by 2020, Pakistan will be 4th most populous country in terms of diabetic patients as they are more prone to stroke. The stroke affects almost all the age groups and genders from neonates to elder people. Its risk increases with the increase of age. A stroke causes major social and economic burden on the country. Acute stroke and coronary syndrome have some similarities that helps in understanding how restoration of normal blood flow and arterial occlusion can decrease mortality rate and prevent disability. Stroke is a syndrome and has two types, ischemic (85% of cases) and hemorrhagic (15% of cases). The severity of strokes defines that either they are minor or transient ischemic in nature.

Though the data on this topic regarding the prevailing issue in Pakistan is scarce, we have tried in this narrative review to collect particulars based upon clinical trials, diagnosis and management. The consequences of ischemic stroke are myriad, ranging from physical disability like paralysis to death, psychological, social and economic burden.

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INTRODUCTION:

Stroke is a debilitating illness which leads a significant proportion of people to death all across the globe. According to a rough estimate, its incidence is increasing in Asia. Among all Asian countries, Pakistan is currently sharing a noteworthy weight of this devastating disease which is indirectly adding burden in form of exponential expenditures of finances, resources, health services, manpower and economy as a whole.^{1,2}

A stroke is a medical emergency with ischemic stroke the most common type. When a blood clot plugs or blocks a blood vessel in the brain, then a stroke occurs. This plug prevents the proper flow of blood to the brain cells, and within minutes the cell began to die. Stenosis, another cause of stroke, is narrowing of the artery. Atherosclerosis is the reason behind this and it forms plaques inside the arteries. When blood supply to the brain is interrupted, then Transient Ischemic Attacks (TIAs) occur. Having a TIA means the person is at risk of ischemic stroke.

Diabetes and hypertension are considered as traditional risk factors of ischemic stroke in the Asian countries. As per a survey, in Pakistan the ratio of diabetic and hypertensive patients is increasing at an exponential rate. Unfortunately, the majority of the population is unaware of their critical condition and the risk factors leading towards other harmful diseases.^{3,4}

The objective of this review article is to gather the facts related to ischemic stroke and its different aspects in the underdeveloped country, Pakistan, where resources and health care system is unprogressive.⁵

Comparison of Ischemic Stroke and Coronary Syndrome

Ischemic stroke syndrome has multiple causes like 25% arteroembolic, 25% cardioembolic large artery disease, 25% small artery disease and 25% other causes linked with different illnesses. In contrast, rupture or erosion of an atherosclerotic plaque becomes the reason of coronary syndrome. This plaque in turns causes arterial obstruction.

The obstruction of vessels in both these diseases provides an outline that how blood flow prevention leads to cell death and other abnormalities.

In ischemic stroke, arterial occlusion is usually embolic. It can either be cardioembolic due to atrial fibrillation or heart valvular disease, or it can be arteroembolic due to disease in vertebral artery or in the extracranial cervical carotid.^{6,7} The process of plaque rupture in the extracranial cervical carotid arteries is similar to that of in the coronary

arteries, but the results are visible in arteroembolism, the distal embolization of thrombus to the brain instead in situ vessel occlusion.

Studies are showing that acute coronary syndromes have analogous arteroembolic mechanisms to ischemic stroke. As the latter has embolism in distal coronary arteries and the former has in extracranial carotid artery. It is found that intrinsic small vessel disease is also linked in a quarter of ischemic strokes, but the depth of its mechanism is still under study. Its pathological examination has revealed that microatheroma with plaque rupture is the most significant cause of occlusion.^{8,9}

Some other least common causes of coronary and ischemic syndrome are founded, include vasospasm, arterial dissection, hypercoagulable states and vasculitis.

Symptoms of Acute Ischemic Stroke

The symptoms of the ischemic stroke depend entirely upon the affected region of the brain, which in turn is defined by the damage of the arterial anatomy involved. There are many features to define an ischemic or hemorrhagic stroke, but none of them are sufficiently discriminatable to allow clinical diagnosis.

The best way to diagnose a stroke is via brain and neurological imaging. However, awareness among the masses regarding the stroke diagnosis can be spread using the acronym FAST, which stands for facial droop, arm drop, speech disturbance and time. Headache, facial or neck pain can also be ancillary symptoms, but most of the strokes are painless.

Sudden onset of stroke is easy, it includes the peaking within a few minutes, and acute neurologic symptoms. Stroke in left hemisphere has symptoms like aphasia, right hemianopia and hemiparesis in the right hemisphere, left hemispacial neglect, left hemianopia and left hemiparesis.

Diagnosis of Ischemic Stroke:

The best way to identify a stroke is via brain and neurovascular imaging. The current trend which is fast and widely available is the computed tomography (CT) of the head. CT can provide over 95% accurate results regarding hemorrhagic strokes when discussed and interpreted by experts. Head CT can also rule about two third cases in which ischemic changes might can occur, but this scan is insensitive towards minor stroke.^{10,11}

Another option is Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), it has greater spatial resolution to detect ischemic illness in the brain; it can detect the brain is either under the harm of transient ischemic attack or minor ischemic stroke. Usually for all acute

stroke syndromes, CT angiography along with noncontrast head CT is recommended by the experts. For the management of minor to major, transient to acute all kinds of ischemic strokes, the identification of occluded intracranial vessels, evaluation of extracranial vertebral, carotid, aortic arch and proximal great vessels is mandatory.

National Stroke Care and Management Guidelines:

In 2010, national stroke care and management guidelines were presented for the appropriate strategic care of patients with stroke in Pakistan. The silent features of the guidelines are:

1. Prehospital identification and stroke triage: To decrease delay in hospital care presentation of the patient by track record of admittance and careful patient management.
2. In-hospital management and care: Careful protocol follow up at subsequent stroke care steps.¹²

Emergency Department

- Rapid breathing, airway and circulation management
- Quick assessment of neurological deficits
- Identification of present risk factors
- Determination of time of onset stroke symptoms
- NHISS stroke scale standardization
- At the facility if rtPA is available, use of NINDS recommendations for survival from stroke: 10 min for emergency evaluation by the physician, 10 min specialist assessment, and 25 min for CT scan.
- An emergency non contrast head CT
- Control of blood pressure to below 185/ 110 mm Hg
- Ancillary testing, blood tests for diabetes, abnormal lipids, coagulopathy and screen test for renal failure
- FDA approved treatment protocol for thrombolysis within 3 to 5 hours of symptoms for acute ischemic presenting

Other Parameters

- Control of core body temperature
- Maintenance of glucose level between 80 and 140 mg/dL
- Urgent anticoagulation measures for preventing the recurrent and progress of stroke, halting worsening of ischemic stroke are not recommended. This step is regardless of the aetiology of stroke
- Oral administration of antiplatelet therapy with aspirin 160–325 mg/ daily started within 48 hours of onset of ischemic stroke
- Free fluids should be avoided and isotonic hydration should be given. Nutritional supplementation is not important

- Aspiration evaluation is important prior to diet initiation
- Screening is important for the detection of swallowing problems with water swallowing tests is imperative. Patients who have swallowing issues should get a nasogastric tube for feed and medications.
- Patients who are unable to mobilize independently should ideally be provided with a special pressure relieving mattress instead of a standard hospital mattress. There should be standing instructions for repositioning every 2 hours
- Deep vein thrombosis should be avoided in immobilized patients. In the acute phase, use of low- dose subcutaneous heparin is suggested. In cases where the risk of intracerebral hemorrhage is high, intermittent compression devices are recommended
- Avoid use of steroids
- Early rehabilitation
- Avoid use of neurotonics and neuroprotection

➤ Posthospital management

- Aspirin dose in a range from 75 to 300 mg is efficacious in stroke prevention. Clopidogrel is recommended to patients with concomitant peripheral vascular disease or to those intolerant to aspirin
- Combination of aspirin and clopidogrel should only be used for TIA, as it has higher risk of symptomatic ICH
- Those who have intermittent of continuous atrial fibrillation, dose adjusted warfarin is recommended in a ration 2–3
- Long term blood pressure control, antihypertensive therapy is preferable. Therefore the drug should be prescribed as per the financial status of the patient
- Regular physical activity and strict dietary control
- Patients with TIA or ischemic control with increased cholesterol level, the risk of coronary artery disease or evidence of an atherosclerotic origin need physician consultation for lifestyle modifications
- Physicians should stay in touch with the patients, ask them to quit smoking and restrict dietary salt intake
- Poststroke depression identification and management is extremely important to prevent cognitive impairment. Selective

serotonin reuptake inhibitor (SSRIs) have good efficacy, low negative impacts, which makes this drug good and valuable for patients

Future Outlooks

Pakistan is lagging behind developed countries in stroke neurology, acute and ischemic stroke in particular. But there has been some positive changes in recent times. Aga Khan University Hospital, in Karachi, has the facility to provide state of the art stroke management. It has successfully treated a number of patients with thrombolysis case. In Islamabad, Shifa International Hospital is positively contributing in the research field regarding acute ischemic stroke. It has also successfully treated various patients with this illness in the recent years with IV thrombolysis.^{13,14}

The future of stroke seems promising in Pakistan with the steps taken by the federal government and the establishment of the Centre of Neurosciences in Lahore. Multiple large scale projects are under work and the Pakistan Institute of Medical Sciences has put forward its efforts to increase the awareness regarding stroke among the masses of the country and help other hospitals to provide with basic health services in this niche.

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